

Table S1. Results of SNP methylation hydrolysis by GC-MS

Sample	Connection	Derivative	MW	Relative molar ratio (%)
SNP	t-Fuc(p)	1,5-di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-6-deoxy-2,3,4-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl fucitol	293	0.428
	t-Xyl(p)	1,5-di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl xylitol	279	2.977
	t-Man(p)	1,5-di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -methyl mannitol	323	6.549
	t-Glc(p)	1,5-di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -methyl glucitol	323	15.534
	t-Gal(p)	1,5-di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -methyl galactitol	323	38.592
	1,4-Fuc(p)	1,4,5-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-6-deoxy-2,3-di- <i>O</i> -methyl fucitol	321	0.567
	1,2-Xyl(p)	1,2,5-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-3,4-di- <i>O</i> -methyl xylitol	307	2.700
	1,2-Man(p)	1,2,5-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-3,4,6-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl mannitol	351	1.482
	2,3-Fuc(p)	1,2,3,5-tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl-6-deoxy-4- <i>O</i> -methyl fucitol	349	3.747
	1,2-Gal(p)	1,2,5-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-3,4,6-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl galactitol	351	20.307
	1,6-Glc(p)	1,5,6-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl glucitol	351	1.336
	1,4-Glc(p)	1,4,5-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,6-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl glucitol	351	3.008
	1,6-Gal(p)	1,5,6-tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl galactitol	351	0.750
	2,4-Gal(p)	1,2,4,5-tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl-3,6-di- <i>O</i> -methyl galactitol	379	0.383
	3,6-Man(p)	1,3,5,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,4-di- <i>O</i> -methyl glucitol	379	0.940
	2,6-Gal(p)	1,2,5,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl-3,4-di- <i>O</i> -methyl galactitol	379	0.702

Table S2 Assignment of ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts of sugar residues in SNP

Sugar residues	chemical shift (ppm)								
		1	2	3	4	5	6a/6b	CH3 of NAC	CO fo NAC
A β-D-Galp-(1→	H	4.34	3.56	3.68	3.96	3.66	3.77/--		
	C	105.86	75.40	75.50	72.19	74.24	63.43		
B →2)-α-D-Galp-(1→	H	5.23	3.91	4.09	3.93	3.51	3.68		
	C	98.81	75.88	71.11	71.89	71.60	63.40		
C α-D-Glcp-(1→	H	4.87	3.47	3.66	3.32	3.88	3.75		
	C	100.95	71.60	72.19	72.27	69.17	63.30		
D →4)-α-D-Glcp-(1→	H	5.33	3.44	3.97	3.65	3.34	3.69		
	C	100.33	69.55	71.60	76.11	71.81	63.45		
E →3,4)-β-D-GlcpNAc(1→	H	4.55	3.74	3.55	3.44	3.42	3.99	2.02	
	C	104.18	57.40	80.31	83.33	73.36	63.42	25.14	175.4

Figure S1. Total ion flow diagram of SNP

Figure S2. ¹H-spectrum of SNP

13C

Figure S3. C-spectrum of SNP

Figure S4. COSY spectrum of SNP

Figure S5 HSQC spectrum of SNP

Figure S6. HMBC spectrum of SNP

Figure S7. NOESY spectrum of SNP